

STATISTICAL PREDICTION OF TENSILE CREEP FAILURE TIME FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

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ABSTRACT

A prediction method for the statistical creep failure time of polymer composites using the statistical static strengths of polymer composites measured at various temperatures is proposed based on Christensen's model of viscoelastic crack kinetics. Then the static strengths at various temperatures under tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP are measured experimentally and statistically using numerous resin impregnated carbon fiber strands (CFRP strands). The creep failure time of unidirectional CFRP is predicted statistically based on the prediction method using statistical static strengths at various temperatures. Finally, the creep failure times of unidirectional CFRP at a constant load and a temperature are measured experimentally and statistically using many CFRP strands for comparison with predicted values. Results show that the statistical creep failure time of unidirectional CFRP is predictable using the statistical static strengths of unidirectional CFRP, because the experimental creep failure times agree well with the predicted ones.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been used for the primary structures of airplanes, ships, automobiles and other vehicles for which high reliability must be maintained during long-term operation. Therefore, an accelerated testing methodology is strongly anticipated for the long-term life prediction of CFRP structures exposed to actual environmental temperatures, water, and other influences.

The mechanical behavior of matrix resin of CFRP exhibits time and temperature dependence, called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass transition temperature T_g , but also below T_g . Consequently, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of CFRP depends strongly on time and temperature [1–5]. Our earlier reports have proposed the formulation of statistical static, creep, and fatigue strengths of CFRP based on the viscoelasticity of matrix resin [6–7].

The tensile strength along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP constitutes important data for the reliable design of CFRP structures. The authors developed a test method for creep and fatigue strengths as well as the static strength at elevated temperatures for resin-impregnated carbon fiber strands (CFRP strands) combined with T300-3000 and epoxy resin [8]. Additionally, the authors developed a test method for the CFRP strand of T800-12000 and epoxy resin with highly reliable co-cured tab. The temperature-dependent tensile strength of this CFRP strand was evaluated successfully [9].

Our most recent study undertook the prediction of statistical creep failure time under tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP performed using CFRP strands of T800-12000 and epoxy resin. The statistical creep failure time of CFRP strands at a constant load and temperature was predicted using statistical results of static tensile strengths of CFRP strands measured at various temperatures and the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin. The predicted results did not

quantitatively agree well with the experimentally obtained results measured using creep tests for CFRP strands [10].

As described herein, the proposed method of predicting the statistical creep failure time under the tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP from the statistical static strengths of unidirectional CFRP measured at various temperatures is clearly valid quantitatively. First, a method of predicting the statistical creep failure time of CFRP from the statistical static strengths of CFRP measured at various temperatures is proposed again based on Christensen's model of viscoelastic crack kinetics [11]. Second, many CFRP strands combined with T300-3000 and epoxy resin as specimens for unidirectional CFRP are prepared using simultaneous molding to elicit stable and uniform mechanical and thermal properties. Third, the static strengths of unidirectional CFRP are experimentally and statistically measured at various temperatures using these CFRP strands. Then the creep failure time of unidirectional CFRP is predicted statistically using the statistical static strengths at various temperatures based on the predicting method. Finally, the creep failure times of unidirectional CFRP at a constant load and a temperature are measured experimentally and probabilistically using these CFRP strands for comparison with the predicted ones.

2 STATISTICAL PREDICTION OF CREEP FAILURE TIME OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

We have proposed the formulation for the statistical static strength σ_s of CFRP based on the viscoelasticity of matrix resin, as shown in the following equation in our previous paper [7] as

$$\log \sigma_s(P_f, t, T) = \log \sigma_0(t_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha_s} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - n_R \log \left[\frac{D^*(t, T)}{D_c(t_0, T_0)} \right], \quad (1)$$

where P_f signifies the failure probability, t denotes the failure time, t_0 represents the reference time, T is the temperature, T_0 stands for the reference temperature, σ_0 and α_s respectively denote the scale parameter and the shape parameter on Weibull distribution of static strength, n_R is the viscoelastic parameter, and D_c and D^* respectively represent the creep and viscoelastic compliances of matrix resin. The viscoelastic compliance D^* for the static load with a constant strain rate is shown by the following equation.

$$D^*(t, T) = D_c(t/2, T) \quad (2)$$

The statistical static strength σ_s is shown by the following equation by substituting Equation (2) into Equation (1).

$$\log \sigma_s(P_f, t, T) = \log \sigma_0(t_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha_s} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - n_R \log \left[\frac{D_c(t/2, T)}{D_c(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (3)$$

The relation between the creep failure time and the static failure time can be shown by Figure 1 [10]. This figure shows the creep strength and the static strength versus failure time. The creep strength curve is obtainable by horizontally shifting the static strength curve by the amount $\log A$. Therefore, the statistical creep strength σ_c is shown by the following equation.

$$\log \sigma_c(P_f, t, T) = \log \sigma_0(t_0, T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha_s} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - n_R \log \left[\frac{D_c(At/2, T)}{D_c(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (4)$$

The failure probability of unidirectional CFRP under a constant creep stress σ_{c0} can be shown by the following equation from Equation (4).

$$P_f = 1 - \exp(-F), \log F = \alpha_s \log \left[\frac{\sigma_{c0}}{\sigma_0} \right] + \alpha_s n_R \log \left[\frac{D_c(At/2, T_0)}{D_c(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (5)$$

The shifting amount $\log A$ determined by the slope of the static strength curve is shown by the following equation.

$$\log A = \log(1 + 1/k_R) \quad (6)$$

Figure 2(a) shows the slope m_R of the creep compliance of matrix resin against time. Figure 2(b) shows the slope k_R of the static strength of CFRP against failure time. Slope k_R is obtainable from the following equation [10].

$$k_R = n_R m_R \quad (7)$$

Figure 1: Time shifting between static strength and creep strength [10]

Figure 2: Slope against time for creep compliance of matrix resin and static strength of CFRP [10]

3 MOLDING OF CFRP STRANDS

A CFRP strand which consists of high strength type carbon fiber T300-3000 (Toray Industries Inc.) and a general purpose epoxy resin jER828 (Mitsubishi Chemical Corp.) was molded using a

filament winding system developed by the authors [8]. Actually, 200 specimens of CFRP strands were molded at one time using this system. The composition of epoxy resin and the cure condition of CFRP strand are presented in Table 1. The diameter and the gage length of CFRP strands are approximately 1 mm and 200 mm, respectively. The glass transition temperatures T_g of the epoxy resin in CFRP strand was 165°C determined from the peak of loss tangent against temperature at 1 Hz using the DMA. The fiber volume fraction of CFRP strand was 58.5% ascertained from the weight of CFRP strands.

Carbon fiber strand	Composition of resin (weight ratio)	Cure schedule
T300-3000	Epoxy: jER828 (100)	100°C × 5 h
	Hardener: MHAC-P (103.6)	+ 150°C × 4 h
	Cure accelerator: 2E4MZ (1)	+ 190°C × 2 h

Table 1: Composition and cure schedule of CFRP strand T300/jER828

4 CREEP COMPLIANCE OF MATRIX RESIN AND STATIC STRENGTH OF CFRP STRAND

The dimensionless creep compliance D_c/D_{c0} measured at various temperatures is shown on the left of Figure 3. The long-term D_c/D_{c0} at $T=120^\circ\text{C}$ is obtained by shifting horizontally those at various temperatures, as shown in the right of Figure 3 [10]. The reference temperature and time are selected as $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$ and $t_0=1$ min in this study. The creep compliance at reference temperature and reference time D_{c0} is 0.33 (GPa)⁻¹. The dashed curve is the dimensionless viscoelastic compliance D^* of matrix resin under the constant strain rate at $T=120^\circ\text{C}$. The maximum slope in this figure is $m_R = 0.28$ shown in Equation (7).

The static tension tests for CFRP strand were conducted at four temperature levels, 25°C, 120°C, 135°C, and 150°C with cross-head speed 2 mm/min. The tensile strength of the CFRP strand σ_s is obtained using the following equation.

$$\sigma_s = \frac{P_{\max}}{t_e} \rho \quad (8)$$

Therein, P_{\max} is the maximum load [N]. ρ and t_e are the density of the carbon fiber [kg/m³] and the tex of the carbon fiber strand [g/1000 m].

Figure 4 shows the Weibull distributions of the static strength of CFRP strand (a) T300/jER828 and (b) T800/jER828 for the comparison. α_s is the shape parameter and β_s is the scale parameter of CFRP strand in this figure. Although the scale parameter decreases according to the temperature raise, the shape parameter maintains almost a constant value for the both CFRP strands.

Figure 5 presents the dimensionless static strength of CFRP strand σ_s/σ_0 against the dimensionless viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin D^*/D_{c0} for both CFRP strand T300/jER828 and T800/jER828. For both CFRP strands, the relation of σ_s/σ_0 against D^*/D_{c0} can be shown by the straight line with the slope of n_R which is the viscoelastic parameter in Equations (1), (3), and (5).

Figure 3: Dimensionless creep compliance of matrix resin at $T=120^{\circ}\text{C}$ [10]

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Weibull distributions of static tensile strength of CFRP strand
(a) T300/jER828 and (b) T800/jER828

Figure 5: Statistical static strength of CFRP strand against viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin
 (a) T300/jER828 and (b) T800/jER828

5 CREEP FAILURE TIME OF THE CFRP STRAND

Creep failure tests of CFRP strand were conducted using the specially designed creep failure testing machine [10]. The applied creep stress σ_{c0} was 3,007MPa (84% of scale parameter of static strength at 25°C). Test temperature was 120°C . Number of specimens was 30. Results of the creep failure tests are presented in Figure 6.

The predicted creep failure probability against failure time calculated by substituting the parameters on Table 2 in Equations (5), (6), and (7) is also shown in Figure 6. The predicted statistical creep failure time agrees with the experimental data. The dotted curve is the predicted curve when the environmental temperature $T = 119^\circ\text{C} = 120^\circ\text{C} - 1.0^\circ\text{C}$ is assumed. $\Delta T = 1.0^\circ\text{C}$ is the difference of glass transition temperature of matrix resin and CFRP strand. The dotted curve agrees well with the experimental data. This fact clarified that the statistical creep failure time of unidirectional CFRP can be predicted quantitatively from the statistical static strengths of unidirectional CFRP and the creep compliances of matrix resin at various temperatures.

Scale parameter of static strength of CFRP strand at 25°C: σ_0	3,580 MPa
Shape parameter of static strength of CFRP strand: α_s	29
Viscoelastic parameter of matrix resin: n_R	0.0472
Slope of viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin: m_R	0.28
Slope of static strength of CFRP strand against failure time: k_R	0.0132
Logarithmic time shifting factor: $\log A$	1.89

Table 2: Parameters for statistical creep failure time prediction for CFRP strand T300/jER828

Figure 6: Creep failure probability against failure time for CFRP strand T300/jER828

6 CONCLUSION

We proposed a prediction method for statistical creep failure time under tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP using the statistical static tensile strength of CFRP strand and the viscoelasticity of matrix resin based on Christensen's model for viscoelastic crack kinetics. The applicability of the prediction method was confirmed using the steps presented below.

1. The method of predicting the statistical creep failure time of CFRP from the statistical static strengths of CFRP measured at various temperatures is proposed based on Christensen's model of viscoelastic crack kinetics.
2. Static strengths at various temperatures under tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP were measured experimentally and statistically using many CFRP strands.
3. The creep failure times of unidirectional CFRP were predicted probabilistically using statistical static strengths at various temperatures based on the prediction method.
4. The creep failure times of unidirectional CFRP at a constant load and a temperature are measured experimentally and statistically using many CFRP strands for comparison with the predicted ones.

Results show that the statistical creep failure time of unidirectional CFRP can be predicted using the statistical static strengths of unidirectional CFRP because the experimental creep failure times agree well quantitatively with the predicted ones.

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